

Integration of Artificial Intelligence Tools in Human Resource Management for Administrative Effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

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Abstract

This study investigated integration of artificial intelligence tools in human resource management for administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. Three objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of this study was 2257 lecturers consisting of 1585 from Rivers State University and 672 from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The sample size of this study was 339 consisting of 207 lecturers from Rivers State University and 132 lecturers from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education derived from Taro Yamane's formula and simple random sampling technique. The instrument of the study was a self-developed questionnaire titled: "Integration of Artificial Intelligence Tools in Human Resource Management for Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire" which was face and content validated by two experts in Measurement and Evaluation and Department of Educational Management in Rivers State University. Cronbach Alpha statistics was used to establish the reliability of the instrument which yielded reliability indexes of 0.84, 0.87 and 0.80. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while z-test was used in testing the formulated null hypotheses at .05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that integration of HireVue AI-driven in recruitment, Workday AI-driven in staff performance management and Coursera in staff training enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities to a high extent. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that university administrators should adopt HireVue AI-powered recruitment tool that can automate and streamline the hiring process so as to ensure the strategic acquisition of talent in a competitive academic environment.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence Tools, Administrative Effectiveness, Human Resource Management, Recruitment, Staff Performance, Staff Training.

This paper should be referenced as follows:

Amie-Ogan, O. T., & Major-jack, B. (2026). Integration of artificial intelligence tools in human resource management for administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 19(2), 260-274. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21204552>

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INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary digital era, the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has significantly transformed organizational operations across various sectors, including education. Accordingly, universities as dynamic institutions, are increasingly leveraging digital innovations to enhance administrative effectiveness and optimize human resource management (HRM) practices. The path-way to actualizing digital emancipation of universities has become most critical in the 21st Century as universities strive for global competitiveness in ranking and visibility across the globe. More so, university education is that aspect of tertiary education saddled with the responsibility of producing intellectuals, researchers and required general workforce needed for societal development (Paul & Amadi, 2017). There is no gainsaying that, human resource management, being central to the attainment of university goals, requires strategies that should improve planning, recruitment, selection, employee engagement, performance appraisal, staff training and development. In corroboration, Pan et al. (2023) stressed that the integration of AI tools in HRM has emerged as a pivotal tool for streamlining administrative functions, ensuring data-driven decisions and fostering organizational agility. The strategic integration of AI tools in HRM practices, especially within the context of universities in Rivers State, Nigeria, holds immense potential for addressing the prevalent administrative challenges such as inefficient recruitment processes, delayed staff appraisal and poor talent management.

The integration of AI tools into HRM aligns with global trends in educational administration. Globally, universities are embracing AI technologies to facilitate smart decision-making, talent acquisition and workforce planning. These practices emphasize the transformative potential of AI in fostering organizational competitiveness, resilience and administrative effectiveness (Guenole & Feinzig, 2022). The World Economic Forum (2023) underscored the increasing reliance on AI to address skill gaps, manage workforce diversity and enhance leadership development in complex institutional environments. In the Nigerian context, while AI adoption is still in its nascent stage, policies are being initiated which are aimed at digitizing education management systems. These innovations do not only reduce administrative workload but also enhance staff satisfaction and productivity, which are essential for achieving administrative effectiveness (Bassi & Li, 2021). In Rivers State universities, where the pressure to meet global academic standards is mounting, integrating AI tools in HRM represents a strategic response to the call for improved administrative effectiveness.

Administrative effectiveness refers to the ability of administrators to achieve organizational goals efficiently and ensure that resources are aligned towards optimal performance. According to Drucker in Cameron (2018), administrative effectiveness is the capacity of an administrator to make the right decisions and ensure their successful implementation. Katz and Kahn in Northouse (2019) posited that administrative effectiveness refers to the ability of an administrator to coordinate and integrate various organizational processes to achieve efficiency and productivity. Furthermore, Owens and Valesky (2015), asserted that an effective administrator is one who can adapt to changing educational policies, manage resources judiciously and maintain a high level of staff motivation. Effective administration, therefore, requires not only sound decision-making but also the ability to translate plans into actions that yield desired outcomes. This approach suggests that administrative effectiveness is not just about enforcing rules or managing resources but also about fostering innovation, collaboration and a shared vision within an organization. The integration of AI tools into HRM practices presents a timely and strategic opportunity for

enhancing administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. Given the persistent administrative challenges in these institutions, AI tools offers a pathway to modernize HR operations, support data-informed decision-making and promote institutional sustainability. Nonetheless, the success of this integration depends on the extent to which universities understand and align AI capabilities with their specific administrative contexts.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is broadly defined as the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, particularly computer systems. Kaplan and Haenlein in Amie-Ogan (2025) defined AI as a system's ability to interpret external data correctly, to learn from such data and to use that learning to achieve specific goals and tasks through flexible adoption. These include not only logical reasoning and problem-solving, but also pattern recognition, language translation and even emotional interpretation. Davenport and Ronanki (2018) described AI as a collection of technologies ranging from machine learning to robotics that can enhance organizational efficiency by automating complex tasks, analyzing large datasets and offering predictive insights.

Remarkably, Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools have emerged as transformative systems that enhance the operational and strategic dimensions of human resource management (HRM) in contemporary institutions of learning, including universities. Russell and Norvig (2021) defined AI tools as software systems that perceive their environment and take actions that maximize their chances of achieving specific goals. This background of understanding highlights the ability of AI to support decision-making and optimize processes through intelligent automation. Particularly, the use of Artificial Intelligence tools in human resource management in educational settings would support tasks such as recruitment, performance appraisal, staff training and development thereby improving administrative efficiency through personalized learning/training experiences and optimal workforce planning. In the 21st Century, educational institutions and administrative systems increasingly encounter operational challenges hence, the adoption of AI tools' present a viable path towards enhancing decision-making, human resource management and service delivery. AI tools provide HR professionals with the technological infrastructure to manage staff more effectively, predict workforce needs, and align human resources with strategic institutional objectives.

Human resource management is a systematic approach towards the acquisition, motivation, development and control of the human resources in the organization. Amie-Ogan (2023) defined human resource management as the process of obtaining, motivating, retaining and controlling employees to maximally achieve organizational and personal goals. According to Armstrong and Taylor (2023), HRM can be defined as a strategic and integrated approach to the development and well-being of people working in organizations. The management of human beings is one of the most vital and crucial managerial divisions in organizations typified by schools. It is charged with the responsibility of handling people. The main responsibility is to recruit, induct, train, supervise and motivate employees. The aim of human resource management in the school system is to support the organization in attracting, retaining and developing the kinds of personnel which the organization would require for effective execution of its task and duties. Without an adequate, skilled and well-motivated workforce operating within a sound human resource management programme, development as well as effective teaching and learning is not possible (Amie-Ogan & Epelle, 2021). Administrative effectiveness depends on recruitment, selection, induction, placement, performance management, training and development and motivation of staff which human resource management portrays. It is only by integrating AI tools such as predictive analytics, automated interviews (e.g. HireVue), Workday's

AI-driven performance management and personalized training platforms (e.g. Coursera) into HRM practices that university administrators can improve the recruitment process, monitor staff performance and training more effectively and responsively.

The recruitment process remains a critical component of human resource management because it determines to a large extent the quality of personnel that would be selected to drive institutional performance and administrative efficiency. The introduction of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into recruitment through digital platforms such as HireVue has significantly reshaped how organizations attract, assess and select candidates. HireVue is an AI-powered video interviewing and talent assessment tool that leverages machine learning algorithms to evaluate candidates' verbal and non-verbal cues such as tone, language choice, facial expressions and communication style during interviews (Thompson & George, 2021). Traditional recruitment processes are not only time-consuming but also prone to human bias, which can compromise the objectivity and fairness of candidate evaluation. By replacing manual screening with automated analysis, HireVue eliminates the constraints of human bias and time inefficiency that often hinder administrative performance in traditional recruitment. This automation enhances the objectivity of the hiring process, ensures consistency in assessment and supports administrative transparency, which are all essential components of administrative effectiveness. In addition to improving fairness and efficiency, HireVue significantly can provide instant responses to applicant inquiries, guide candidates through the application process and keep them informed about their application status (Sharma, 2021). This contributes to administrative effectiveness by optimizing the use of institutional time and human resources. According to Johnson (2022), HireVue also enhances candidate experience, which is an increasingly important indicator of an institution's administrative reputation. Through the offering of structured and flexible virtual interviews, the platform allows candidates to participate remotely and at their convenience, thereby increasing accessibility and inclusivity in the recruitment process. Correspondingly, Miller (2020) observed that AI recruitment systems such as HireVue contribute to institutional credibility by demonstrating fairness and professionalism which are qualities that enhance public trust in administrative processes. Consequently, through its automation, predictive intelligence and user-centered design, HireVue strengthens recruitment accuracy, enhances fairness, minimizes administrative bottlenecks and contributes to a more effective and responsive administrative system.

Performance management remains one of the most challenging aspects of human resource administration because it directly affects employee motivation, productivity and institutional goals attainment. Observations over the years have proven that traditional performance appraisal systems are often plagued by inconsistencies, delayed feedback and administrative inefficiencies that undermine overall effectiveness. The integration of AI tools such as 'Workday' has, however, revolutionized this process by introducing real-time, data-driven and continuous evaluation mechanisms. Workday is an AI-enabled human resource management platform that uses predictive analytics, natural language processing and machine learning to assess, monitor and enhance employee performance (Smith & Taylor, 2022). It functions through intelligent data collection, which provides administrators with actionable insights on employee engagement, performance trends and skill gaps. This ensures that administrators can make informed, timely decisions regarding promotions, training needs and task allocation, thereby improving overall administrative effectiveness.

One of the most significant ways Workday enhances administrative effectiveness is through its capacity to generate continuous feedback loops between supervisors and

subordinates. Unlike traditional annual appraisals that delay performance reviews, Workday facilitates real-time evaluations and instant feedback, allowing employees to correct performance deficiencies immediately (Nguyen, 2021). This immediacy fosters accountability and strengthens the alignment between employee output and institutional goals. Kaur and Aggarwal (2023), asserted that AI-driven performance management systems like Workday facilitate continuous performance monitoring through the automated collection of data from various sources such as emails, project management tools, attendance records and peer feedback. Workday also contributes to administrative effectiveness by automating several aspects of employee performance tracking and reporting (Chamorro et al., 2019). It generates dashboards and analytics that display performance indicators in real time, thus reducing manual paperwork and improving information accessibility for decision-making. For instance, an administrator can easily identify underperforming staff, recognize high achievers and forecast future workforce needs using Workday's predictive models (Johnson, 2022). This proactive management approach strengthens institutional responsiveness and allows leaders to anticipate rather than merely react to performance issues. Moreover, Workday supports administrative accountability by maintaining a transparent and auditable record of employee evaluations, thereby enhancing trust and fairness within the organization (Meijerink, Bondarouk & Lepak, 2021). As a result, Workday's integration into HR processes fosters a performance culture built on data accuracy, efficiency and continuous improvement, which are core indicators of administrative effectiveness.

Training is essential for building the competencies of staff and maintaining institutional relevance in an increasingly digital and knowledge-driven world. AI-powered learning platforms such as Coursera have transformed staff training by providing adaptive, data-driven and personalized learning experiences. Coursera uses artificial intelligence algorithms to analyze employee learning behavior, job requirements and performance records to recommend tailored courses that address individual and institutional skill needs (Brown & Chen, 2022). Personalization of training ensures that the staff receive relevant and targeted training that directly improves their job performance and contributes to institutional effectiveness. Unlike conventional training programmes that often take a one-size-fits-all approach, Coursera's AI-enhanced platform aligns professional development initiatives with specific organizational goals and employee roles. In the context of educational and administrative institutions, Coursera enhances administrative effectiveness by reducing training costs, improving learning flexibility and increasing access to high-quality educational resources (Min & Lim, 2022). In addition, staff can take courses remotely, which minimizes disruptions to daily operations and allows institutions to upskill a large number of employees simultaneously.

Unlike traditional workshops and seminars, AI-based systems like Coursera provide 24/7 access to training resources through digital platforms, allowing staff to learn at their convenience and without interrupting their daily responsibilities (Almalki & Aziz, 2021). This accessibility of learning contribute to an agile workforce that can adapt quickly to policy changes, technological updates and institutional reforms. According to Johnson (2022), the AI analytics within Coursera enable administrators to monitor staff progress, completion rates and learning outcomes in real time thus making it easier to evaluate the impact of training investments. The data generated provides valuable insights for strategic planning and policy formulation related to human resource development. In this way, AI integration transforms training from a routine administrative function into a strategic tool for institutional advancement. Moreover, Coursera promotes a culture of lifelong learning and adaptability, which are crucial for sustainable

administrative effectiveness (Dhanalakshmi & Rani, 2022). By encouraging employees to engage in continuous skill development, administrators build a more innovative, efficient and responsive workforce. Furthermore, AI tool such as Coursera can support the upskilling and reskilling of staff to meet emerging demands in digital literacy, data management and educational technology, a necessity in an era where remote and blended administrative functions have become commonplace (Owolabi, Olaniyan & Adebayo, 2021). Through data-driven learning personalization, real-time performance tracking and scalable delivery mechanisms, Coursera significantly strengthens the human capacity foundation upon which effective administration is built.

Statement of the Problem

In today's rapidly evolving digital landscape, universities are under increasing pressure to enhance administrative effectiveness and optimize the management of human resources. In Rivers State Universities, human resource management (HRM) practices remain largely traditional, relying heavily on manual systems that are often inefficient, time-consuming and prone to errors. These outdated approaches hinder the ability of institutions to attract, develop and retain qualified personnel, which in turn affect administrative effectiveness.

In spite of global trends highlighting the transformative potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in modernizing HRM functions such as recruitment, performance appraisal, staff training and workforce analytics, many universities in Rivers State have been to adopt these innovations (Ahmad et al., 2022). The lack of integration of AI tools into HRM systems in these institutions present a significant challenge to achieving administrative excellence. This gap is particularly evident in areas such as recruitment, staff performance management and staff training.

Furthermore, institutional barriers such as limited digital infrastructure, insufficient technical expertise and resistance to change have continued to inhibit the integration of AI tools into HRM practices. As universities strive to meet increasing demands for accountability, efficiency and global competitiveness, the inability to harness AI tools for strategic HRM threatens to widen the gap between institutional goals and actual performance outcomes. Given these concerns, there is a pressing need to investigate how AI tools can be effectively integrated into HRM practices to enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. Hence the study investigated, "Integration of Artificial Intelligence Tools in Human Resource Management for Administrative Effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate integration of artificial intelligence tools in human resource management for administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. Specifically, the study sought to:

- Examine the extent to which integration of HireVue as an AI-driven tool in recruitment enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.
- Determine the extent to which integration of Workday as an AI-driven tool in staff performance management enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

- Ascertain the extent to which integration of Coursera as an AI-driven tool in staff training enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- To what extent does integration of HireVue as an AI-driven tool in recruitment enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?
- To what extent does integration of Workday AI-driven in staff performance management enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?
- To what extent does integration of Coursera in staff training enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses further guided the study:

- There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of HireVue an AI-driven tool in recruitment enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.
- There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of Workday as an AI-driven tool in staff performance management enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.
- There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of Coursera as an AI-driven tool in staff training enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 2257 lecturers consisting of 1585 from Rivers State University and 672 from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The sample size of this study was 339 consisting of 207 lecturers from Rivers State University and 132 lecturers from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. Taro Yamane's formula was used to determine the sample size while simple random sampling technique was adopted in sampling lecturers from both universities. The instrument for the study was a self-developed questionnaire titled: "Integration of Artificial Intelligence Tools in Human Resource Management for Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (IAITHRMAEQ)" which was structured on a four point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE) with 4 points, High Extent (HE) with 3 points, Low Extent (LE) with 2 points and Very Low Extent (VLE) with 1 point respectively.

The instrument was face and content validated by two experts in Measurement and Evaluation and Department of Educational Management in Rivers State University and tested for

reliability using Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded reliability indexes of 0.84, 0.87 and 0.80. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions with a criterion mean of 2.50. Items rated 2.50 and above signified ‘High Extent’ while items rated below 2.50 denoted ‘Low Extent’. The hypotheses posed in the study were analyzed using z-test at 0.05 level of significance. Where the z-calculated value was above z-critical value of ± 1.96 , the hypothesis was rejected and below was accepted.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent does integration of HireVue as an AI-driven tool in recruitment enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of HireVue as an AI-driven tool in recruitment enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

S/N	Items	RSU N=207		Rmk.	IAUE N=132		Rmk.
		Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1.	HireVue AI-driven helps to analyze vast volumes of applicant data which reduces the time to hire	3.25	0.88	HE	3.33	0.83	HE
2.	HireVue AI-driven tool provides instant responses to applicant inquiries, guide candidates through the application process and keep them informed about their application status which improves administrative effectiveness	3.17	0.71	HE	3.11	0.69	HE
3.	HireVue AI-driven tool supports more efficient, fair and strategic recruitment practices by automating routine tasks, reducing bias, providing actionable insights and improving candidate engagement	3.24	0.71	HE	3.33	0.71	HE
4.	HireVue A-driven tool system detects patterns and predicts a candidate’s future performance based on historical data, further aiding in the selection of individuals who align with institutional goals	3.46	0.76	HE	3.47	0.69	HE
5.	HireVue AI-driven tool helps to identify relevant applicant qualifications on time and rank candidates based on predefined criteria	3.07	0.67	HE	2.56	0.88	HE
Grand Mean and SD.		3.24	0.75	HE	3.16	0.76	HE

Data in Table 1 for research question 1, revealed that all the items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 had mean scores of 3.25, 3.17, 3.24, 3.46 and 3.07 with standard deviation 0.88, 0.71, 0.71, 0.76 and 0.67 for lecturers from Rivers State University and 3.33, 3.11, 3.33, 3.47 and 2.56 with standard deviation 0.83, 0.69, 0.71, 0.69 and 0.88 for lecturers from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. In summary with grand mean scores of 3.24 and 3.16 which were above the criterion

mean of 2.50, this indicated that to a high extent integration of HireVue AI-driven tool in recruitment enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Research Question 2: To what extent does integration of Workday AI-driven tool in staff performance management enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of workday AI-Driven tool in staff performance management enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

S/N	Items	RSU N=207		Rmk.	IAUE N=132		Rmk.
		Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
6.	Workday AI-driven tool provides real-time insights into employee performance, enabling managers to identify trends, recognize high performers and address underperformance promptly	3.22	1.09	HE	2.71	0.83	HE
7.	Workday facilitates continuous performance monitoring through the automated collection of data from various sources such as emails, project management tools, attendance records and peer feedback	2.76	0.67	HE	2.84	1.12	HE
8.	Workday AI-driven tool through predictive analytics forecast future performance trajectories, allowing HR units to proactively design targeted professional development programmes	2.98	0.73	HE	3.12	0.64	HE
9.	Workday AI-driven tool identifies skill gaps and recommend training interventions tailored to individual needs, thereby supporting employee development in a structured and measurable manner	2.74	0.89	HE	2.66	0.71	HE
10.	Workday AI-driven tool improves employee engagement and motivation through personalized feedback mechanisms and real-time goal tracking that keeps staff members informed about their progress and expectations.	3.11	0.78	HE	2.88	0.55	HE
Grand Mean and SD.		2.96	0.83	HE	2.84	0.77	HE

Data in Table 2 above for research question 2, revealed that all the items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 had mean scores 3.22, 2.76, 2.98, 2.74 and 3.11 with standard deviation 1.09, 0.67, 0.73, 0.89 and 0.78 for lecturers from Rivers State University and 2.71, 2.84, 3.12, 2.66 and 2.88 with standard deviation 0.83, 1.12, 0.64, 0.71 and 0.55 for lecturers from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. In summary with grand mean scores of 2.96 and 2.84 which are above the criterion mean of 2.50. This result indicated that to a high extent integration of Workday AI-driven tool in staff performance management enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Research Question 3: To what extent does integration of Coursera AI-driven tool in staff training enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of Coursera AI-driven tool in staff training enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

S/N	Items	RSU N=207		Rmk.	IAUE N=132		Rmk.
		Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
11.	Coursera AI-driven tool enables the creation of responsive training programmes aligned with institutional priorities which improve administrative effectiveness	2.90	0.82	HE	2.99	0.89	HE
12.	Coursera AI-driven tool modifies training content in real time based on user interactions and performance feedback	2.89	0.74	HE	3.22	0.77	HE
13.	Coursera AI-driven tool supports the upskilling and reskilling of staff to meet emerging demands in digital literacy, data management and educational technology	3.43	0.83	HE	2.97	1.11	HE
14.	Coursera AI-driven tool provides 24/7 access to training resources through digital platforms, allowing staff to learn at their convenience and without interrupting their daily responsibilities	2.92	0.92	HE	2.67	0.83	HE
15.	Coursera AI-driven tool tracks learning progression over time, analyzes patterns in staff behavior and performance and generates actionable insights for HR administrators	3.21	0.78	HE	2.98	0.79	HE
Grand Mean/SD		3.07	0.82	HE	2.97	0.88	HE

Data in Table 3 above for research question 3, revealed that all the items 11, 12, 13, 14 and 15 had mean scores 2.90, 2.89, 3.43, 2.92 and 3.21 with standard deviation 0.82, 0.74, 0.83, 0.92 and 0.78 for lecturers from Rivers State University and 2.99, 3.22, 2.97, 3.67 and 2.98 with standard deviation 0.89, 0.77, 1.11, 0.83 and 0.79 for lecturers from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. In summary with grand mean scores of 3.07 and 2.97 which are above the criterion mean of 2.50. The result achieved indicated that to a high extent integration of Coursera AI-driven tool in staff training enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of HireVue AI-driven tool in recruitment enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Table 4: z-test analysis of difference between the mean and standard deviation ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of HireVue AI-Driven tool in recruitment enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

Respondents	N	Mean	SD	Df	SL	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
RSU	207	3.24	0.75	337	0.05	0.89	± 1.96	Accepted
IAUE	132	3.16	0.76					

Table 4 shows a summary of mean, standard deviation and z-test analysis of difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of HireVue AI-driven tool in recruitment enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. The z-test calculated value of 0.89 was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 , using 337 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted which implies that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of HireVue AI-driven tool in recruitment enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

H0₂: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of Workday AI-driven tool in staff performance management enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Table 5: z-test analysis of difference between the mean and standard deviation ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of workday ai-driven tool in staff performance management enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

Respondents	N	Mean	SD	Df	SL	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
RSU	207	2.96	0.83	337	0.05	1.33	± 1.96	Accepted
IAUE	132	2.84	0.77					

Table 5 shows a summary of mean, standard deviation and z-test analysis of difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of Workday AI-driven tool in staff performance management enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. The z-test calculated value was 1.33 and the z-critical value was ± 1.96 , using 337 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. Since the z-calculated value was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis was accepted. This implies no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of Workday AI-driven tool in staff performance management enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

H0₃: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of

Coursera AI-Driven Tool in staff training enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Table 6: z-test analysis of difference between the mean and standard deviation ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of coursera AI-driven tool in staff training enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

Respondents	N	Mean	SD	Df	SL	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
RSU	207	3.07	0.82	337	0.05	1.00	±1.96	Accepted
IAUE	132	2.97	0.88					

Table 6 shows a summary of mean, standard deviation and z-test analysis of difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of Coursera AI-Driven tool in staff training enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. The z-test calculated value was 1.00 and the z-critical value was ± 1.96 , using 337 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. Since the z-calculated value was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis was accepted. This implies no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of Coursera AI-driven tool in staff training enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings on research question 1 in Table 1 revealed that, to a high extent, integration of HireVue AI-driven tool in recruitment enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities with grand mean values of 3.24 and 3.16. Hypothesis 1 in Table 4 revealed no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of HireVue AI-driven tool in recruitment enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities with z-calculated value of 0.89 which was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 . These findings are in agreement with Sharma (2021), who stated that, AI tools such as HireVue AI-driven tool can provide instant responses to applicant inquiries, guide candidates through the application process and keep them informed about their application status. These findings are also in tandem with Miller (2020), who observed that AI recruitment systems like HireVue contribute to institutional credibility by demonstrating fairness and professionalism, qualities that enhance public trust in administrative processes.

Findings on research question 2 in Table 2 showed that, to a high extent, integration of Workday AI-driven tool in staff performance management enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities with grand mean values of 2.96 and 2.84. Again, data on hypothesis 2 in Table 5 revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of Workday AI-driven tool in staff performance management enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities with a z-calculated value of 1.33 which was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 . These findings are in tandem with Meijerink, Bondarouk and Lepak (2021), who asserted that Workday AI-driven tool can forecast future performance trajectories,

allowing HR units to proactively design targeted professional development. Also, in support of this result Kaur and Aggarwal (2023) asserted that AI-driven performance management systems like Workday facilitates continuous performance monitoring through the automated collection of data from various sources such as emails, project management tools, attendance records and peer feedback which ensures effective administration.

Findings on research question 3 in Table 3 showed that, to a high extent, integration of Coursera AI-driven tool in staff training enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities with grand mean values of 3.07 and 2.97. Again, findings on hypothesis 3 in Table 6 revealed that, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which integration of Coursera AI-driven tool in staff training enhances administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities with z-calculated value of 1.00 which was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 . These findings corroborate with Min and Lim (2022), who stated that Coursera in staff training enhances administrative effectiveness by reducing training costs, improving learning flexibility and increasing access to high-quality educational resources. Also, in support Almalki and Aziz (2021) asserted that unlike traditional workshops and seminars, AI-based systems like Coursera provide 24/7 access to training resources through digital platforms, allowing staff to learn at their convenience and without interrupting their daily responsibilities.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that to a high extent integration of AI-driven tools such as HireVue in recruitment, Workday in staff performance management and Coursera in staff training enhance administrative effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. Precisely, AI tools offer a pathway to modernize HR operations, support data-informed decision-making and promote institutional sustainability.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- University administrators should adopt HireVue AI-driven recruitment tool so as to automate and streamline the hiring process while ensuring strategic acquisition of talent in a competitive academic environment.
- Rivers State universities should integrate the Workday AI-driven tool in staff performance management as this would provide real-time feedback, continuous monitoring and data-informed evaluation while ensuring that performance metrics are clearly defined and aligned with academic and administrative targets.
- Rivers State universities should integrate Coursera AI-driven tool in their staff training so as to provide adaptive learning and intelligent tutoring of staff and to deliver personalized, flexible and on-demand training content to academic and administrative staff.

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